

CODE 325**HEAT TRANSFER THROUGH ANCHORING ELEMENTS IN A REAR-VENTILATED RAINSCREEN INSULATION SYSTEM FOR FAÇADE RETROFIT****Arregi Goikolea, Beñat¹; Garay Martinez, Roberto²; Riverola Lacasta, Alberto³; Chemisana Villegas, Daniel⁴**1: Sustainable Construction Division
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Universitat de Lleidae-mail: daniel.chemisana@macs.udl.cat, web: <http://www.udl.cat>**KEYWORDS:** thermal insulation; ventilated façade; thermal bridge; finite element method**ABSTRACT**

Rear-ventilated rainscreen façade insulation systems are becoming a popular retrofit solution in Southern European climates, due to their good thermal performance in both winter and summer conditions. In these assemblies, the substructure of the new cladding is anchored to the original building, thus puncturing the thermal insulation. This study assesses the impact of such thermal bridges on the overall thermal performance of the external wall. The renovation of a conventional Spanish wall construction with a ventilated façade is used as a case study, featuring an anchoring system with L-shaped aluminium brackets. Two scenarios have been assessed: in the first one these brackets are fixed onto both the reinforced concrete slabs and the existing brickwork of the building, while in the second one they are anchored solely to the structural slabs. Simplified one-dimensional calculations are compared with two- and three-dimensional numerical models. Results indicate that anchoring elements can account for a substantial increase in heat flow. If the additional heat transfer through the anchoring elements is not taken into account, the energy savings delivered by the renovation could be considerably lower than expected by calculations, resulting in an increase of energy consumption over predicted values.

1. INTRODUCTION

The energy-efficient retrofit of the existing building stock constitutes a key part of the strategy of the European Union for reducing its energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions. The Energy Efficiency Directive [1] requires EU countries to draw up long-term national strategies for building renovation, articulated through dedicated National Energy Efficiency Action Plans drafted by each Member State.

Insulating the external envelope is one of the most efficient interventions for achieving such reductions in energy consumption. Existing walls are renovated by adding thermal insulation, most often either externally or internally, in order to slow the rate of heat transfer through the wall. National building regulations often specify insulation requirements by setting a limit on the U-value, a measure of steady-state thermal transmittance for a plane section of the wall obtained through calculation [2].

As we move towards high insulation requirements, unforeseen heat loss at poorly insulated junctions becomes more significant. A study carried over various European countries [3] showed that up to 20% of overall energy consumption can be attributable to thermal bridges. However, this additional heat loss is not included within U-values, and its extent is rarely measured or considered in practice. This disregard is a potential contributor to a disparity between predicted and measured energy use, the so-called 'performance gap' [4]. Many regulations rely on the use of default supplements or tabulated values for thermal bridges [5], but these are likely to underestimate the extent of their heat flow [6]. In contrast, numerical calculation methods allow for a reasonably accurate prediction of additional heat flow at junctions [7].

Rear-ventilated rainscreen insulation systems have been shown to be a well-performing solution for façade retrofits in Southern European climates [8][9]. Despite a higher cost than rendered external insulation systems, the presence of the ventilated cavity provides an important advantage in warm weather, by dissipating excess heat through stack effect. In such systems, a thermal insulation layer is attached to the external surface of the original wall, separated by a ventilated air layer from a newly installed external cladding. This cladding is supported by a metal substructure which needs to be anchored to the structure of the existing building. Therefore, the anchoring elements of this auxiliary structure necessarily pierce the thermal insulation layer. The aim of the present study is to investigate the absolute and relative impact of these thermal bridges on the overall heat transfer of the insulated wall.

2. CASE STUDY

The renovation of an existing external wall with a ventilated façade insulation system has been selected as a case study. The original wall represents a generic external wall construction commonly found in Spain. It is comprised of an outer leaf of perforated brickwork and an inner leaf of double hollow brickwork, separated by an uninsulated air cavity. The wall is finished with gypsum plaster internally and sand-cement render externally. As both brick leaves sit over the reinforced concrete floor slab at each storey, the slab bridges the external wall assembly and its edge is exposed to the external environment (Fig. 1). This thermal bridge is a very common occurrence in Spanish construction [10].

A conventional rear-ventilated rainscreen system has been studied as a retrofit solution for the aforementioned building envelope. Rigid slabs of polyisocyanurate insulation are attached onto the existing wall. Four different insulation levels have been assessed (with thickness of 50, 100, 150 and 200 mm). The external cladding is separated from the insulation by a ventilated air layer, and supported by an auxiliary structure made of aluminium vertical profiles ($c/c = 1$ m). These profiles are anchored to the existing construction using L-shaped aluminium brackets (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Auxiliary structure of ventilated façade assembly over existing external wall construction

Two different anchoring scenarios have been analysed. In the first one, brackets are fixed onto both the concrete slabs and the outer leaf of the existing wall, with a vertical span of 1.5 m between them. Despite the widespread adoption of this anchoring method for ventilated façades, the ability of the existing brickwork to cope with such point structural loads is seldom assessed, thus potentially compromising the local or global stability of the original wall. In a second scenario, brackets are fastened solely onto the reinforced concrete floor slabs of the original building for greater structural safety. In this case, as the storey height imposes a higher vertical span between anchors (3 m), two brackets are installed at each anchoring point. The shape and density of anchoring brackets are equal for both scenarios assessed.

3. METHOD

The thermal performance of both the original and the renovated wall has been determined using both simplified calculations and numerical thermal models, as detailed below.

3.1. One-dimensional calculation

Initially, a U-value has been calculated for both the original uninsulated wall and the renovated wall containing the new ventilated façade system. For this purpose, a one-dimensional calculation has been carried out following the simplified procedure in [2] as referenced in Spanish Building Regulations [11]. The thermal transmittance U is calculated as the inverse of the total thermal resistance R_T (1), which is simply obtained as the sum of internal and external surface resistances R_{si} , R_{se} and the thermal resistance of each layer of the assembly R_i .

$$U = \frac{1}{R_T} = \frac{1}{R_{si} + \sum R_i + R_{se}} \quad (1)$$

This calculation method considers all layers as plane elements, and so does not take account of the impact of the floor slabs or the anchoring system of the auxiliary frame.

3.2. Two-dimensional thermal modelling

For determining the impact of thermal bridges at junctions with concrete floor slabs, numerical simulations have been carried out applying finite element method analysis over two-dimensional thermal models built with the procedure described in [7] and [12]. The additional heat flow at the junction is calculated as a linear thermal transmittance ψ , obtained as shown in (2) by subtracting the one-dimensional component (U-value multiplied by height of model) from the total linear heat flow L_{2D} through the two-dimensional model in Fig. 2.

$$\psi = L_{2D} - U \cdot h \quad (2)$$

This modelling and calculation procedure has also been carried out for both the uninsulated wall

and the renovated wall.

Figure 2: Two-dimensional model of junction of external wall with floor slab

3.3. Impact of anchoring system

The additional heat flux through aluminium brackets has been determined by numerical simulations using finite element method analysis over three-dimensional thermal models [7]. The additional heat flux through the junction is calculated as a point thermal transmittance χ . If the bracket is fixed onto the outer leaf of the original wall, this value is calculated as per (3), by taking the heat flow L_{3D} through the three-dimensional model in Fig. 3 left and subtracting the one-dimensional component (U -value multiplied by area of model).

$$\chi = L_{3D} - U \cdot A \quad (3)$$

If the bracket is fastened onto the edge of the concrete floor slab, the impact of the two-dimensional thermal bridge of the concrete floor needs to be taken into account. In this case, as shown in (4), both the one-dimensional component (U -value multiplied by area of model) and the two-dimensional component (linear thermal transmittance multiplied by height of model) are subtracted from the heat flow L_{3D} through the three-dimensional model in Fig. 3 right.

$$\chi = L_{3D} - U \cdot A - \psi \cdot h \quad (4)$$

Figure 3: Three-dimensional models of bracket anchored to wall (left) and to floor slab (right)

3.4. Material properties and boundary conditions

Following the criteria in [2] for well-ventilated air cavities, the thermal resistance of the cladding, the auxiliary structure and the air in the cavity have not been taken into account, and the external and internal surface resistances correspond to still air with horizontal heat flow. Thermal transmittance is not affected by considered boundary temperatures (20 °C internal, 0 °C external), under the assumption that all physical properties are independent of temperature [7].

Thermal properties assumed in the calculations for all materials and surfaces are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Thermal properties considered for surfaces and material components of external walls

Position	Element	Thickness [m]	Thermal conductivity [W/mK]	Thermal resistance [m ² K/W]
Exterior	External surface resistance	-	-	0.13
	PIR insulation	(variable)	0.03	-
	Sand-cement render	0.022	0.8	-
	Perforated brickwork	0.154	0.21	-
	Air cavity	0.110	-	0.18
	Double hollow brickwork	0.077	0.16	-
	Gypsum plaster	0.011	0.8	-
Interior	Internal surface resistance	-	-	0.13
Floor slabs	Reinforced concrete	0.3 (height)	2.2	-
Anchors	Aluminium	-	209	-

3.5. Comparison of heat flows

The steps described above allow for disaggregating the thermal impact of the plane components of the wall, the intermediate floor slab of the original construction, and the anchoring brackets of the ventilated façade. In order to enable a direct comparison among these and quantifying their share on overall heat flow, the results obtained with the different calculation methods described above have been converted into their one-dimensional equivalent. The equivalent thermal transmittance of the wall U_{eq} is defined (5) as the sum of the purely one-dimensional heat flow or U-value, the two-dimensional heat flow (linear thermal transmittance ψ per horizontal distance between brackets d), and the three-dimensional heat flow (point thermal transmittance χ per wall area related to each bracket A).

$$U_{eq} = U + \frac{\psi}{d} + \frac{\chi}{A} \quad (5)$$

4. RESULTS

Results obtained from calculations and numerical simulations are shown in Table 2:

- One-dimensional heat flow, measured by the thermal transmittance U , reduces as insulation levels increase. Since thermal transmittance is defined as the inverse of thermal resistance (1), the greatest reductions in the U-value are achieved by the first mm of insulation, with diminishing returns for greater insulation thicknesses.
- As the thermal insulation is installed against the outer face of the existing wall, it covers both the brickwork and the concrete floor slab, thus achieving continuity. Consequently, the additional heat flow through the slab junction (measured by the linear thermal transmittance ψ) reduces as insulation levels increase.
- In contrast, the additional heat flow through the brackets (measured by their point thermal transmittance χ) rises with insulation thickness, due to the increasingly higher difference in thermal performance for the insulated plane areas of wall and the thermal bridge through the

aluminium brackets. Results show that the intensity of the thermal bridge is ~2-3 times higher if the bracket is anchored to the floor slab than if it is supported onto the outer leaf of the wall. Finally, the heat flow associated with a double bracket at the edge of the floor slab is ~1.5 times higher than for a single bracket in the same location.

Table 2: Results from one-dimensional calculations and two- and three-dimensional thermal models

Insulation thickness [mm]	No insl.	50 mm	100 mm	150 mm	200 mm
Thermal transmittance U [W/m ² K] of external wall	1.050	0.382	0.233	0.168	0.131
Linear thermal transmittance ψ [W/mK] at junction of wall with floor slab	0.444	0.045	0.016	0.008	0.005
Point thermal transmittance χ [W/K] at single bracket anchored to wall	-	0.047	0.061	0.087	0.093
Point thermal transmittance χ [W/K] at single bracket anchored to floor slab	-	0.150	0.155	0.199	0.192
Point thermal transmittance χ [W/K] at double bracket anchored to floor slab	-	0.237	0.253	0.302	0.298

In order to compare and aggregate the heat flow attributed to each of these phenomena, the above results have been converted into their one-dimensional equivalent and expressed in the same units. These results are presented in Table 3 in disaggregated form, and graphically depicted in Figure 4. Finally, Table 4 compares results from simplified one-dimensional calculations and from thermal modelling, including the impact of thermal bridges at floor slabs and anchoring elements.

Table 3: Thermal transmittance per façade area associated with one-, two- and three-dimensional heat flows

Insulation thickness [mm]	No insl.	50 mm	100 mm	150 mm	200 mm
Thermal transmittance [W/m ² K] due to 1D heat flow through external wall	1.050	0.382	0.233	0.168	0.131
Additional thermal transmittance [W/m ² K] due to 2D heat flow through floor slabs	0.148	0.015	0.005	0.003	0.002
Additional thermal transmittance [W/m ² K] due to 3D heat flow through brackets anchored to both floor slabs and brickwork	-	0.066	0.072	0.095	0.095
Additional thermal transmittance [W/m ² K] due to 3D heat flow through brackets anchored to floor slabs only	-	0.079	0.084	0.101	0.099

Table 4: Comparison of thermal transmittance obtained by one-dimensional calculation (U-value) and equivalent thermal transmittance including multi-dimensional heat flow

Insulation thickness [mm]	No insl.	50 mm	100 mm	150 mm	200 mm
U-value of external walls [W/m ² K] considering 1D heat flow only	1.050	0.382	0.233	0.168	0.131
Brackets to floor slabs and brickwork					
Equivalent U-value of walls [W/m ² K] including impact of thermal bridges	1.198	0.463	0.311	0.266	0.228
Increase in heat flow over 1D calculation	14.1%	21.1%	33.3%	58.3%	73.6%
Brackets to floor slabs only					
Equivalent U-value of walls [W/m ² K] including impact of thermal bridges	1.198	0.476	0.323	0.271	0.232
Increase in heat flow over 1D calculation	14.1%	24.6%	38.5%	61.5%	76.9%

Figure 4: Chart of equivalent thermal transmittance per façade area associated with one-, two- and three-dimensional heat flows

Besides one-dimensional heat flow (grey in Fig. 4), measured by the U-value, there is additional heat flow associated with thermal bridges (orange and red in Fig. 4). One-dimensional heat flow reduces as insulation levels increase, but the opposite is true for the additional heat flow associated with thermal bridges. In the case of the original uninsulated wall, the additional heat flow through the concrete slab bridging the assessed wall construction (orange in Fig. 4) amounts to approximately a seventh of the U-value. For the same wall insulated with a ventilated façade, this thermal bridge at the slab is greatly reduced by the new insulation, but the additional heat loss through aluminium brackets (red in Fig. 4) becomes relatively more significant. For the highest insulation level considered (200 mm thickness), the additional heat flow associated with these thermal bridges amounts to over 70% of the wall U-value.

If brackets are anchored to floor slabs only (avoiding fixings to existing brickwork for a greater structural safety) heat flow is only marginally increased for an equivalent geometry and density of anchoring elements.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In ventilated façades, the anchoring elements that support the external cladding pass through the thermal insulation, thereby interrupting its continuity. However, the thermal performance of such insulated assemblies is typically assessed based on a simplified one-dimensional calculation that disregards the impact of these thermal bridges. This study has made use of both simplified calculation methods and multi-dimensional numerical simulation of thermal models, for assessing the impact of anchoring brackets on the overall heat flow of an existing wall renovated with a conventional ventilated façade.

Results have shown that the additional heat flow through these anchoring elements can be substantial, and increases for greater insulation levels. As a result, the reduction in heat loss actually achieved can be much lower than assumed by U-values alone. Disregarding the impact of anchoring elements at design stage can lead to an underestimation of heat flow through the wall, contributing to higher energy consumption than foreseen by calculations.

Despite the many advantages provided by rear-ventilated rainscreen insulation systems, results imply that there is still significant room for improvement in their thermal performance if innovative low thermal bridge solutions are developed for their anchoring elements. These solutions could be based on the addition of thermal breaks, the use of low-conductivity alternatives to aluminium, or topological optimisation for combined thermal and structural performance.

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7. BIBLIOGRAPHY

[1] Directive 2012/27/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on energy efficiency, amending Directives 2009/125/EC and 2010/30/EU and repealing Directives 2004/8/EC and 2006/32/EC (Text with EEA relevance)

[2] ISO 6946:2017. *Building components and building elements – Thermal resistance and thermal transmittance – Calculation methods.*

[3] Erhorn-Kluttig, H. and Erhorn, H. *Impact of thermal bridges on the energy performance of buildings.* ASIEPI report P148, 2009.

[4] De Wilde, P. The gap between predicted and measured energy performance of buildings: A framework for investigation. *Automation in Construction*. Vol. 41 (2014).

[5] ISO 14683:2017. *Thermal bridges in building construction – Linear thermal transmittance – Simplified methods and default values.*

[6] Ferraro, C., Arregi, B. Crossing over: Thermal bridges and the design of the building fabric – a key concern for architects and services engineers. *CIBSE Technical Symposium*, Leicester, 2011.

[7] ISO 10211:2017. *Thermal bridges in building construction – Heat flows and surface temperatures – Detailed calculations.*

[8] Marinosci, C., Strachan, P.A., Semprini, G., Morini, G.L. Empirical validation and modelling of a naturally ventilated rainscreen façade building. *Energy and Buildings*. Vol. 43, Issue 4 (2011).

[9] Marinosci, C., Semprini, G., Morini, G.L. Experimental analysis of the summer thermal performances of a naturally ventilated rainscreen façade building. *Energy and Buildings*. Vol. 72 (2014).

[10] Código Técnico de la Edificación (CTE). *Catálogo de Elementos Constructivos del CTE*. Instituto Eduardo Torroja de Ciencias de la Construcción. March 2010.

[11] Código Técnico de la Edificación (CTE). DA DB-HE/1 *Documento de Apoyo al Documento Básico DB-HE Ahorro de Energía. Cálculo de parámetros característicos de la envolvente*. February 2015.

[12] Código Técnico de la Edificación (CTE). DA DB-HE/3 *Documento de Apoyo al Documento Básico DB-HE Ahorro de Energía. Puentes térmicos*. May 2014.